

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type1_c_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 3:26:24 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	31.58	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.4820	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_t...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type1_c_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 3:26:24 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	9.121	μm	
Min:	-5.506	μm	
Max:	3.615	μm	
Size:	189250	digits	
Spacing:	0.0482	nm	
NM-points ratio:	5.579 % (502086 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_ty...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 3:26:24 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	9.121	μm	
Size:	189250	digits	
Spacing:	0.0482	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	1.032	μm	
Ssk	-1.151		
Sku	7.110		
Sp	3.607	μm	
Sv	5.514	μm	
Sz	9.121	μm	
Sa	0.7037	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.8308	%	
Smc	0.9461	μm	
Sxp	2.876	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	20.01	μm	
Str	0.6657		
Std	42.25	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.2457		
Sdr	2.644	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.06199	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	1.008	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.06199	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.6724	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.8097	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.1984	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	5.661	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.8866	µm
Mean density of furrows	3870	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	89.99	°
Second direction	135.0	°
Third direction	44.96	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	87.68	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

